

Real-Time, In-Situ Cure Monitoring of Advanced Aerospace Composites Using A Fibre Optic Sensor Based on FTIR Spectroscopy

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With the advent of automated process control, a significant demand has developed for sensing techniques for non-intrusive, real-time monitoring of resin cure reactions in structural components. The development of an intrinsic fibre optic chemical sensor based on evanescent-wave absorption is reported. This fibre optic sensor, which permits remote chemical analysis by near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, has been used to monitor the cure of an advanced aerospace epoxy resin by coupling to a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer.

Key Words: Fibre Optic Sensor, In-Situ Analysis, Chemical Analysis, Cure Monitoring, Process Control, Infrared Spectroscopy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is a high demand for sensors and systems which provide real-time, on-line monitoring and chemical analysis of various industrial manufacturing processes. Optimisation of the manufacturing process results in increased production, reduction in production times, fewer rejects and shut-downs, improved product quality, and reduced costs. Fibre optic chemical sensors are promising for this application due to their dielectric properties (immunity to electromagnetic interference), their remote sensing capabilities, their high sensitivity, their applicability in hazardous and harsh environments, and, in the case of intrinsic sensors, rapid response times. A particular advantage of these sensors is their small size which permits their easy and non-intrusive embedding in a variety of host materials.

The cost of optical fibre components and systems is rapidly decreasing and sensing techniques are being refined for practical field use. As a result, fibre optic sensors will soon be accepted as a reliable and inexpensive measurement tool in many sensing applications.

Optical fibres are compatible with the manufacturing process of many materials without significant modification of the material's mechanical or chemical properties or the fibre's own dielectric nature. Fibre optic sensors which are embedded in materials or structures offer the advantage of providing both the sensing element and the signal path. The majority of fibre optic chemical sensors are based on the absorption or fluorescence of light. [1] Many of these are extrinsic sensors, that is to say that the fibre simply delivers the light to the sensing cell and then returns it to the detector/analyser. Intrinsic techniques, on the other hand, also involve the fibre in the actual sensing mechanism.

Composite materials are seeing an increased use in consumer products and structural components (ie., automobiles, marine vehicles, aircraft, and spacecraft). Over the last few years, new and

improved techniques for manufacturing these materials have lowered the manufacturing costs significantly. However, it is widely believed that optimum manufacturing conditions will only be achieved by real-time feedback process control using in-situ, non-invasive sensors. To date, fibre optic sensors have been used to monitor the cure of polymeric materials by measuring the difference between the refractive index of the cured and uncured composition [2], by attaining real-time Fourier Transform mid-infrared absorption spectra using an intrinsic [3] or extrinsic [4] infrared-transmitting chalcogenide-glass evanescent fibre optic sensor, by Raman spectroscopy using an extrinsic silica optical fibre configuration [5], by evanescent-wave fluorimetry using an intrinsic silica fibre optic sensor [6], and by Fourier Transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy in the near infrared (NIR) using silica optical fibres coupled to both ends of a microcapillary curing cell [7,8].

The most promising technique, with the least complications and limitations, appears to be FTIR spectroscopy. The development of infrared-transmitting optical fibres (ie., fluoride and chalcogenide glass) has generated much interest in remote sensing. However, the optical and mechanical properties of these glass fibres are not yet optimised, rendering them difficult to handle. Silica optical fibres, on the other hand, seem to have been largely overlooked for their NIR-transmitting potential in NIR absorption spectroscopy applications, where several useful absorption bands are present. [7-9] This paper reports on the development of an intrinsic silica fibre optic sensor based on evanescent-wave FTIR spectroscopy. The sensor has demonstrated the capability to detect and monitor absorption bands of particular molecules in liquids and during the cure of an epoxy resin.

2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION AND THEORY

2.1. The structure of optical fibres

Optical fibres are dielectric wave guiding devices used to confine and guide light. The majority of optical fibres used in sensing applications have silica glass cores but some special materials, such as sapphire, fluoride glasses, chalcogenide glasses, lead glasses and Neodymium doped silica are utilised for specialised applications.

The core is surrounded by a dielectric material called the cladding. The cladding's refractive index must be lower than the core to satisfy Snell's Law for total internal reflection and thus propagation of the light along the fibre core. The cladding is generally made from silica glass, although for some applications a plastic or doped silica cladding is used. A barrier layer of plastic (the "buffer") is used to jacket the fibre; this provides the fibre with mechanical strength and protects it from damage or moisture absorption. In some sensing applications, a specialised buffer is used to enhance the fibre's measurement sensitivity. **Figure (1)** illustrates a cross-sectional view of an optical fibre.

Figure 1: Cross-sectional view of typical optical fibre.

A simplistic definition of the modes that are guided by an optical fibre can be explained as the locus of all the light rays which are launched at different entry angles into the core of the fibre. For any optical fibre the number of modes that will be guided by the fibre is dependent on core size, the ratio of core/cladding refractive indices, and the wavelength of operation. Depending on the optical property utilised for the sensing application, the number of modes propagated by an optical fibre is an important parameter.

Light that is launched into and confined to the fibre core propagates along the length of the fibre unperturbed unless acted upon by an external influence. Any disturbance of the fibre alters the characteristics of the guided light; such alterations can be monitored, and related to the magnitude of the disturbing influence.

2.2. FTIR Spectroscopy

Infrared spectroscopy is an established optical absorption technique for the detection and monitoring of chemical species; it covers wavelengths in the near-infrared (0.7 μm to 2.5 μm) and the infrared (2.5 μm to 20 μm) regions of the spectrum.

Near infrared technology is well suited for process control because the spectral overtone and combination absorbance bands of many molecules of interest fall in this region. The molecules absorb light energy at frequencies or wavelengths corresponding to the vibrational and rotational frequencies of their bonds. In the NIR, absorption occurs mainly due to C-H, O-H, and N-H bonds. The absorption bands present in a spectral trace can thus be used to identify the chemical species present and can also be used to determine their concentrations. [9]

FTIR spectroscopy is a reliable and accurate technique for monitoring chemical species, concentrations, and reactions. FTIR spectrometers are bulk-optic instruments incorporating a laser and scanning-mirror interferometer which often requires temperature and vibration stabilisation. A broadband blackbody source with a specific phase relation (produced by the interferometer) is transmitted through the sampling medium and the resultant interferogram is Fourier analysed by a CPU to extract the wavelength information (ie., absorption or transmission). Owing to the large and fragile nature of the instruments, FTIR spectrometers are generally confined to the laboratory benchtop. This configuration requires a sample batch of the analyte to be taken from the chemical process assembly to the analytical laboratory; a slow and inefficient procedure. Coupling fibre optic sensors to the FTIR spectrometer improves this procedure substantially by permitting remote, real-time monitoring. The optical air-path and sensing cell in the spectrometer may be replaced by the optical fibres, provided that the fibres have sufficient optical range in the infrared. This technique has been successful in determining FTIR spectra of various compounds. [1, 3, 8, 10, 11]

2.3. Evanescent-Wave Absorption

A beam of light undergoes total internal reflection at the interface between an optical dense medium (waveguide) and an optical rare medium (sensing medium) if the angle of reflection is larger than the critical angle, as determined by Snell's Law. However, some of the light actually penetrates the outer medium and therefore can be absorbed by any absorbing materials present in the medium. The light that penetrates the sample medium is referred to as the *evanescent-wave*. This phenomenon also occurs in optical fibres as the light propagating in the fibre continuously undergoes total internal reflections at the core/cladding interface ($n_{\text{cladding}} < n_{\text{core}}$). The amplitude of the evanescent electric field decays exponentially in the direction outward normal to the boundary given by: [1]

$$E(x) = E(0) e^{-x/d_p} \quad (1)$$

where $E(0)$ is the field at the core/cladding interface, x is the distance into the cladding, and d_p is the penetration depth of the evanescent field as defined by:

$$d_p = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi n_c (\sin^2 \theta_c - \sin^2 \theta_{in})^{1/2}} \quad (2)$$

where λ is the wavelength of propagation, n_c is the refractive index of the core, θ_c is the critical angle, and θ_{in} is the angle of the ray within the fibre. Clearly, the penetration depth can become quite large (within several wavelengths) as θ_{in} approaches the critical angle. **Figure (2)** illustrates this phenomenon.

Figure 2: Evanescent-Wave Penetration.

Attenuated total reflection (ATR) spectroscopy is a well established technique for chemical analysis based on evanescent-wave interactions at the surface of a crystal waveguide. The amount of absorption of the evanescent-wave depends on both the amplitudes of the field and the number of reflections within the optical waveguide. [12-14] Large reflection angles approaching the critical angle result in increased evanescent field amplitudes, and the thickness of the waveguide effects the total number of interface reflections. Optical fibres are therefore well suited as ATR-type cells due to their small diameters.

The evanescent field of an optical fibre generally propagates in the fibre cladding. To gain access to the evanescent-wave either the cladding is totally removed from the fibre so that the epoxy resin acts as the cladding or the cladding is partially removed by polishing or chemical etching so that the evanescent-wave propagates beyond the cladding thickness (d) and thus samples the epoxy resin. [1, 13-17] The epoxy resin is absorptive at particular NIR wavelengths corresponding to the chemical species present. These absorption peaks can be monitored in real-time during cure and their intensities can be related to the degree of cure. If the outer medium has a refractive index greater than the core index, then the beam of light undergoes refraction at the interface. Assuming a smooth and uniform side-polish, such that $d \leq d_p$, the anticipated value of the evanescent field would be in the order of 10% of the original field strength. [18] Figure (3) illustrates the fibre optic evanescent wave absorption technique.

Figure 3: Fibre optic evanescent wave absorption technique.

It has been found that tapering optical fibres also increases the absorption sensitivity. [1, 12, 14, 17] The two mechanisms which lead to this improvement is that higher order modes are generated due to the increased reflection angles in the tapered section and that many more reflections per unit length occur in the smaller diameter section. The enhancement is believed to be greater than or equal to $(b_0/b_1)^2$, where b_0 is the untapered fibre radius and b_1 is the tapered fibre radius at the waist of the taper. [17]

2.4. Epoxy Resin Systems

A common matrix system used in composite materials consists of tetra glycidyl-4, 4'-diaminodiphenyl methane (TGDDM) epoxy resin with 10 to 17 %-by-weight diaminodiphenyl sulphone (DDS) hardener. The structure of these compounds is graphically illustrated in Figure (4), as well as the epoxy and amine components of interest.

The three main reactions of this system during cure are illustrated in Figure (5). [7,8]

Figure 4: Composition of TGDDM and DDS.

Figure 5: Three main reactions of Ciba Geigy epoxy resin during cure.

Therefore, it should be possible to monitor the on-going reactions or the cure process of the composite material by monitoring the growth and decrease of the absorption bands relating to the following bond forming and breaking mechanisms:

1. disappearance of primary amine $-\text{NH}_2$
2. growth of hydroxyl groups $-\text{OH}$
3. disappearance of the epoxy ring ⌢
4. disappearance of secondary amine $-\text{NH}$

Graham et. al. [7,8] have conducted material cure studies concerned with the cure reactions of Ciba Geigy TGDDM-based epoxy resin MY720 and hardener DDS. They identified the main-species NIR absorption bands for the material using an extrinsic fibre optic transmission microcapillary tube technique. The major bands of interest during cure are illustrated in Figure (6).

Figure 6: Near infrared band assignments of MY720 in the 0.7 μm to 2.2 μm range.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

This paper reports on the development and proof-of-principles of an intrinsic fibre optic chemical sensing technique. Further refinement of the sensing system, as well as concentration and kinetic-reaction studies is the focus of on-going work.

An intrinsic fibre optic configuration based on evanescent-wave absorption was used to sample chloroform (CHCl_3) as well as to monitor the cure of a polymeric material; Ciba Geigy Araldite epoxy. NIR spectra were obtained by coupling the optical fibres to an FTIR spectrometer.

Communications grade, multimode optical fibre optimised for the NIR region was side-polished using a technique described by Hussey and Minelly [19] involving a motor-driven polishing wheel. The fibre was stripped of its outer coating (buffer) and suspended on the edge of the one inch diameter polishing wheel under tension. The surface contact of the fibre on the polishing wheel varied between 6-10 mm. The wheel was driven at approximately 100 revs/min and was lubricated with liquid paraffin. The abrasive wheel used was a diamond impregnated resin jewellery polishing wheel with particle size of $9\ \mu\text{m}$. Diamond pastes of particle size 5, 3, and $1\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively, were used at various stages of the polishing procedure. A HeNe laser and silicon detector were used to monitor the losses due to polishing and the paraffin 'bleeding-out' the evanescent field. A 6 dB loss of the laser power resulted in polishing very nearly to the core/cladding interface. Control of the procedure was limited to tolerances of $\pm 5\ \mu\text{m}$ within the core/cladding interface.

The sensing system layout is illustrated in Figure (7). The fibre optic sensor was coupled to a Mattson Sirius 100 FTIR spectrometer by using two XYZ translation stage fibre optic couplers. A tungsten source was focused into one end of the optical fibre and the other end was placed directly in front of a InSb photo-voltaic detector cooled to 77 K. The polished section of the fibre was approximately mid-way through the 2 meter length of the fibre. Each spectra was composed of 32 averaged scans. A relatively constant background of 4% was measured for the sensors in air. Subsequently, the sensors were placed in contact with the chemical (chloroform) or resin (epoxy) to be monitored. The Ciba Geigy Araldite was cured at room temperature.

Figure 7: Experimental Setup.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The refractive index of the chloroform was supplied by the manufacturer as 1.4457. The refractive index of the optical fibre is approximately 1.46, therefore no difficulties were experienced with absorption sensitivities. Figure (8) illustrates an absorption spectra collected for chloroform. The binary and ternary combination bands appear in their characteristic locations [9], indicating that the sensing technique was operating correctly. Chloroform is often used as a NIR solvent due to its relatively low absorbance below $2\ \mu\text{m}$. A strong absorbance band was encountered in all spectral scans using the multimode fibre at $6200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ ($1.613\ \mu\text{m}$). This is believed to be caused by some absorbing material in the cladding of the fibre. Concentration studies were not carried out at this stage as we were primarily concerned with demonstrating sensor operation.

Figure 8: FTIR Spectroscopy Absorption Spectra of Chloroform.

Graham et. al. [7,8] have identified the main-species NIR absorption bands for the material using an extrinsic fibre optic transmission microcapillary tube technique. They identified the major bands of interest during cure as an amine (NH_2) band at 5067 cm^{-1} ($1.974 \mu\text{m}$) and a hydroxyl group (OH^-) band around 4860 cm^{-1} ($2.058 \mu\text{m}$) with an isobestic point between them at 4980 cm^{-1} ($2.008 \mu\text{m}$). Their technique was very effective due to their experimental configuration where the entire beam of light was launched through the sensing medium, thus achieving maximum sensitivity.

First, the refractive index of the Araldite was measured using a Carl Zeiss Abbe refractometer. It was found to be 1.517 for the fully cured epoxy. Assuming a 3% change in refractive index during cure [2], the refractive index of the uncured epoxy is still higher than the optical fibre. Theoretically, therefore, the sensitivity would be reduced by approximately 90%, but still within the resolution of the spectrometer. The amine band was not detected, however, a band was detected at 4855 cm^{-1} which corresponds with the hydroxyl band. Figure (9) illustrates the spectra as a function of cure time at 20°C . Hydroxyl ions are formed very quickly and in abundance in the Araldite cure. The increasing absorbance at 4855 cm^{-1} , but the absence of the amine band, may suggest that the observations are either due to an increasing concentration of hydroxyl ions or an increasing penetration of hydroxyl ions into the fibre. This phenomenon is currently being investigated in conjunction with the characteristic hydroxyl absorption peak (Si-OH) of optical fibres at 7194 cm^{-1} ($1.39 \mu\text{m}$).

Figure 9: FTIR Spectroscopy Absorption Spectra of Ciba Geigy Araldite Cure.

5. CONCLUSION

An intrinsic, multimode silica optical fibre has been demonstrated as a chemical sensor. The sensing technique is based on evanescent-wave FTIR spectroscopy in the NIR. The change in hydroxyl peaks as a function of curing time was detected in a Ciba Geigy Araldite.

The sensitivity of the sensor for monitoring absorption bands during the cure of epoxies was relatively poor. This is attributed to the higher refractive index of the epoxy than the optical fibre. The sensor is being further developed in order to increase sensitivity. Sensitivity will be improved through the use of higher refractive index fibres, the use of single or few mode fibres, increased sensing gauge length, and a tapered sensing region. An additional advantage of the higher refractive index glasses will be their extended NIR-transmitting properties.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Dr. Geoff Stone and Chris Byrne of Telecom Research Labs for their technical assistance and the use of their FTIR spectrometer.

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